

Pension Reforms and Pensioners' Welfare in Nigeria: A Study of Contributory Pension Scheme

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Abstract

This research aims to analyze the influence of contributory pension schemes on the welfare of retirees in Nigeria. The plight of public sectors pensioners who have devotedly served the nation has been a cause of significant concern throughout history. Existing literature on pension reform and workers' welfare in Nigeria's public sectors illustrates the continued hardships faced by pensioners after retirement, despite various reforms and changes in pension schemes. Regrettably, the newly adopted contributory pension system has failed to provide relief to retirees, resembling its predecessor in shortcomings and leading to a loss of confidence among many retirees regarding the pension model's ability to address the challenges faced by retirees in Nigeria. These issues can be attributed to various setbacks encountered by pension schemes in Nigeria, which include inadequate funding, influx of ineligible pensioners, political interference, employer insincerity, inaccurate record-keeping leading to corruption, lack of funding and non-payment of pensions, significantly dampening retirees' welfare. Against this backdrop, the study investigates the extent to which the contributory pension reform has impacted the welfare of retirees in selected Federal Establishments in Nigeria. To achieve this objective, the research adopted survey and descriptive research designs, drawing data from both primary and secondary sources. The productive theory of pension developed by Dorsey, Cornwel, and Mapherson in 1998 was utilized as the theoretical framework. Among the study's findings was the identification of issues such as non-remittance of the 7.7% counterpart contribution by most employers, payment

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delays, weak administration, lack of record-keeping, and corruption, which reminiscent the major features of the old pension models. As a result, the study recommends, among others, the efficient management of investments in the pension fund to achieve a sufficient, robust return on investment, ultimately enhancing the welfare package for retirees in Nigeria.

Keywords: Pension, Pension scheme, Pension reforms and Pensioners welfare.

Introduction

The issue of pension has garnered significant attention across numerous countries in recent decades. Particularly in recent times, policymakers in many countries have increasingly focused on pension as a means of facilitating privately funded retirement income savings for an aging workforce (Lachman, 2013). The concept of "pension" has been defined in various ways by different authors. For example, Odia and Okoye (2012) defined it as the amount paid by the government or a company to an employee who, after working for a specific period, is deemed too old, ill, or has reached the statutory retirement age. It is the retirement benefit provided to elderly employees by their employer or the organization they previously worked for, upon meeting specific criteria. The primary goal of pension is to ensure that the retiree's source of living does not cease at retirement, aligning with the views of Barr and Diamond (2006) that the major goal of pension is to enable continued consumption beyond one's work-life, providing a means for continuous income and consumption during retirement.

Historically, the origin of the official pension plan is traced back to the poor law in England which was the first publicly financed social security systems developed in the late 16th century in England from a series of legislature Acts known as "Poor Laws" which gave rise to the social insurance in Europe and social security in the United States (Ugwu, 2006). Under these laws, local governments built large alms-house facilities that housed the old age or persons that are unfit for work. The laws also established work houses and facilitated public housing for the employed.

In Nigeria, the history of pension administration dates back to 1951 following its introduction by the former colonial master for European workers and with a

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retrospective effect back in January 1946 (Odia and Okoye, 2012). The act was referred to as the pension ordinance and it became the origin of modern pension administration in Nigeria and the first pension law in the history of the country. However, with subsequent review and reform, the Pension Reforms Act of 2004 brought into limelight the new pension scheme in Nigeria which is a defined contributory scheme unlike the old scheme which was largely defined benefits. Thus, the need for the replacement of the pay-as-you go (old pension scheme) with the contributory pension scheme became necessary as a result of unsatisfying nature of the old schemes due to the unpleasant experiences faced by retirees and pensioners, and the huge pension liabilities. Sadly, the old pension scheme (defined benefit pension scheme) was characterized by delay in the payment of the pension benefit as and when due, a huge pension debt of about N2.06 billion as of December 2005, the rigorous processes involved prior to the pension payment, poor record of pensioners, inadequate funding, inadequate subvention and grant, as well as poor documentation, among others (Oladipo and Fashagba, 2012).

Thus, the replacement of the old pension scheme with the new pension scheme by the Nigerian government (as recommended by the World Bank) was as a result of its failure to meet the goal of providing regular income to the retirees as and when due (Orenstein, 2008). However, to ensure effective operation and functionality, the contributory pension system has been structured in such a way that all the employers and employees in both public and private organizations are mandated to contribute at least 7.5% each of the emoluments of the employee into a Retirement Savings Account for effective and efficient pension administration (Oladipo and Fashagba, 2012). The reason for this arrangement is to ensure financial security after retirement for the betterment of all retirees in Nigeria. Without a doubt, this worthy replacement is expected to answer the many questions the old scheme was no longer able to. Base on the above premise, the study seeks to examine the impact of contributory pension reform on workers' welfare in Nigeria using Akwa Ibom State Civil Service as a case study.

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Statement of the Problem

Employees are entitled to various benefits. Among these benefits is pension. Pension is one of the motivating factors to enhance high productivity, loyalty and discipline of the employees. In order to enforce this compulsory saving toward life after active service, government had designed various policies and schemes to improve the standard of living of pensioners. Sadly, in spite of all these changes, the standard of living of pensioners is not better off than while in active service. The modalities for pension operation in Nigeria have been fraught with damming distortions and challenges. These problems are aggravated with the constant political manipulation, insincerity on the side of employers; inaccurate record keeping that gives opportunities for corruption, lack of funding; and non-payment of pensions which greatly lowered the welfare of retirees. These in turn bring hardship, suffering and untimely death among vast number of Nigerian pensioners.

The devastating sufferings of the vast majority of public sector pensioners who have served the nation meritoriously have become a major concern. Literatures on pension reform and workers' welfare in Nigeria's public sectors have shown that lives after active services have always proven unpleasant for pensioners in spite of various schemes and frequent changes in pension systems. These could be traced to various setbacks encountered by pension schemes in Nigeria right from inception in 1951. These problems range from inadequate fund, proliferation of ineligible pensioners on the payroll, poor management of pension fund, etc.

In order to address this, new pension Act was introduced. However, the advent of Pension Reform Act, 2004 ushered in the operation of contributory pension scheme which received massive support among employees and pensioners who witnessed limitations of the last reform Act. Sadly, instead of bringing new hope to retirees' welfare, the newly adopted pension system followed suits of its predecessor. Many retirees therefore, have lost confidence on the pension model due to its inability to address the problem of retirees in Nigeria. In addition, the contributory pension scheme is characterized by non-remittance of the 7.7% counterpart contribution by most employers, delayed in payment, weak administration, lack of records keeping, corruption, among others, of which were the major features of the old pension models.

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Based on the above stated problems, the study seeks to answer the following questions:

- i. What are the impacts of non-remittance of counterpart contribution by employers on pensioners' welfare in Nigeria?
- ii. How does corrupt practices among pension administrators affect pensioners' welfare Nigeria?
- iii. To what extent has weak administration affect the level of contributory pension scheme efficiency in Nigeria?

Objectives of the Study

While the main objective of the study is to find out whether the contributory pension scheme has had any significant effect on the welfare of retirees from the selected Federal government establishments in Nigeria, specifically, it tends to;

- i. examine the impacts of non-remittance of counterpart contribution by employers on pensioners' welfare in Nigeria;
- ii. examine the extent to which corrupt practices among pension administrators affect pensioners' welfare Nigeria;
- iii. investigate how weak pension administration affect the level of contributory pension scheme efficiency in Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

- i. Non-remittance of counterpart contribution by employers tends to affect pensioners' Welfare in Nigeria.
- ii. Corrupt practices among pension administrators tends to affect pensioners' welfare Nigeria.
- iii. Weak pension administration is likely to affect the efficiency level of contributory pension scheme in Nigeria.

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Review of Conceptual Literature

Concept of Pension

Pension has been diversely defined by different authors in different studies. For instance, Odia and Okoye (2012) saw pension as the amount paid by the government or a company to an employee having been working for some specific period of time, who is considered to be too old or ill to work or has reached the statutory age of retirement. Fapohunda (2013) viewed pension as a system designed to provide the employee of an organization with a means of securing at retirement a standard of living reasonably, consistent with that enjoyed while in service. These definitions show that pension has to do with one's age. Pension is a retirement benefit, unlike gratuity, that provides regular income for the retiree from the time of retirement. Traditionally, a pension has been used as a device to provide sustenance for the old and disengaged employee who may not be able to work again because of his/her old age.

Fashagba (2018) defined pension as a post retirement benefit to an old employee after his/her disengagement from active service. Collaboratively, pension is an arrangement to provide people with an income when they are no longer earning a regular income from employment. It is a tax deferred savings vehicle that allows for the tax-free accumulation of a fund for later use as a retirement income. To Munnell, Aubry, and Crawford (2015), pension is the totality of planned procedures and legal process of security and setting aside of funds to meet the social obligation of care which employers owe their employees at retirement or in case of death. Accordingly, the purpose of pension exercise is to provide employees with regular and stable income after their retirement from service (Wikipedia, 2007). To Adams (2005), pension is the amount paid by government or company to an employee after working for some specific period of time, considered too old or ill to work or has reached the statutory age of retirement. It is a method whereby a person pays into pension scheme a proportion of his earnings during his working life. Neil (1977) defined pension as a retirement provided by the employer to the employee on the condition of retirement, age and ill health. This definition also implies that a pension payment is conditional upon old age, ill health or death. Depending on the form of the pension plan, the retirement benefits either in the form of a gratuity or a pension depends on the years of service. For instance, the 1992

Nigerian Pension Law requires five (5) years of service to qualify for a gratuity and ten (10) years of service for a pension

Importance of Pension on Retirees' Welfare

The roles of pension will be classified (in this study) into two classes, namely the primary role (arising from the main objective of insurance) and the secondary roles that arise from the functions created by the existent pension. The primary role of pension is the provision of retirement income. Pension provides income for the old, who are unable to work again (Kibet and Simiyu, 2016). Pension serves as a medium for saving towards future income when the employee's normal life can no longer be sustained. The secondary roles of a pension are derived from the pension funds created by saving towards a pension payment. The roles include, among other things, financial intermediation and economic development. Several studies on the relationship between economic growth and pension funds have shown that pension funds have a positive impact on economic growth (Farayibi, 2016).

Pension funds reduce the cost of capital (Davis, 2015). Through pension savings, additional funds are made available to the traditional mediums of institutional saving. By applying the microeconomic theory of the price mechanism, an increase in supply forces down the price. Hence, the cost of capital reduces as more funds are created through pension savings. Similarly, Tirimba (2013) observes that pension funds provide less expensive funds for diversification. The existence of pension funds does not only make funds available for investment, but such funds become more affordable and encourage the diversification of the economy.

Finally, pension funds affect economic growth through the provision of additional funds for financing economic activities and stimulate growth. A positive relationship between pension funds and economic growth has been shown in different empirical studies (Edogbanya, Ocheni, and Daniel, 2015). Therefore, a pension plays important roles both for individual retirees and for the economy as a whole.

Types of Pensions

There are two broad pension plans for pension administration. They are the defined benefit pension plan and the defined contribution pension plan. The two are briefly reviewed as follows:

a. Defined Benefit Pension Plan (DB)

Conventionally, the pension benefit has been paid with the defined benefit (DB) pension plan. The defined benefit pays the retiree a monthly pension from retirement to the moment of death by using the number of the years of service and the salary (Curtinn, 2009). In addition, Peifer (2015) opined that the present value of the future pension payment of an employee could be estimated on the four assumptions that include the number of the years of service, the salary, the employee's retirement lifespan and a pension investment gain (where the investment of a pension asset exists). In the Defined Benefit Plan, the sponsoring firm bears the risk of the pension funding, as well as that of the management of the investment.

According to Broadbent, Palumbo and Woodman (2006), the basic features of the defined plan include the following:

- i. the plan promises the employee a monthly pension payment from the date of his/her retirement to the date of his/her death or even still to the date of the death of the employee's spouse;
- ii. the plan usually promises that the formula for calculating the amount of a monthly pension to be paid to the employee shall be that including the years of service with the sponsoring firm as the basis of the computation; hence, the amount of the pension can be predetermined in advance;
- iii. the pension is earned as per each year of service;
- iv. the percentage of the earning of each year of service with the sponsoring firm is what determines the amount of the monthly pension the employee is entitled to from the date of retirement. Workers mobility is discouraged in order to avoid a loss of an accrual pension with a change in employment, thus, enhancing labor stability.

b. Defined Contribution Pension Plan (DC)

Accordingly, Nigerian adoption of the contributory pension scheme followed her pensions reform in 2004. The Defined Contribution Pension Plan has significantly grown since it appeared for the first time (Curtinn, 2009). The plan does not apply any formula for the amount of a monthly pension payment, but rather uses the accumulated fund in the employee's retirement savings account (RSA) at the time of retirement. The employer and/or the employee contribute a percentage of the employee's monthly emolument to the employee's retirement benefit fund. Also, under the defined contribution pension plan, the employee bears more of the risk associated with the pension fund (Broadbent *et al.*, 2006). Unlike the defined benefit pension plan, the risk of the pension fund and the management of investments in it are shifted to the employee.

However, there has been a tremendous shift from the defined benefit pension plan to the defined contribution pension plan in the last few decades. For example, Blommestein, Janssen, Kortleve and Yermo (2009) observed that employers were increasingly turning to the defined contribution where the employee bore the entire income risk. Also, Poterba, Rauh, Venti and Wise (2007) noted that the retirement arrangements of the private sector in the United States that were predominantly the defined benefit had shifted to the defined contribution in the previous two decades, leaving only the public in the defined benefit pension plan.

The features of the defined contribution pension plan include the following:

- i. the defined contribution pension plan provides for a personal individual employee retirement savings account to the employee;
- ii. deriving from the first point mentioned above, the defined contribution pension plan allows room for workers' mobility as the fear of an accrual loss for the years of service put into a job is completely eliminated;
- iii. the defined contribution pension plan does not provide for the knowledge of the amount of a monthly pension in advance.

To Oyedele (2014), other classifications of pensions in Nigeria include:

- i. **Retiring Pension:** This type of pension is usually granted to a worker who is permitted to retire after completing a fixed period of quality service usually 30 to

35 years or on attaining the age of 60 to 65 years for the public service in Nigeria, and 70 years of age for professors and judges.

- ii. **Compensatory Pension:** This type of pension is granted to a worker whose permanent post is abolished and government is unable to provide him with suitable alternative employment.
- iii. **Superannuating Pension:** This type of pension plan is given to a worker who retires at the prescribed age limit as stated in the condition of service.
- iv. **Compassionate Allowance:** This happens when pension is not admissible or allowed on account of a public servants removal from service for misconduct, insolvency or incompetence or inefficiency.

Concept of Pension Reform

The word “reform” means the improvement or amendment of what is wrong, corrupt, unsatisfactory, etc. The use of the word in this way emerges in the late 1700s and is believed to originate from Christopher Wyvill's Association movement which identified “Parliamentary Reform” as its primary aim. Reform seeks to improve the system as it stands, never to overthrow it wholesale.

The pension reform therefore, refers to a set of actions taken to restructure the administration of old age security device of retirees. An important dimension here is its capability to sustain postretirement life. On the one hand, it is capable of financing the livelihood of the retiree and his family over a long time; on the other, it could serve as a financing source for further economic activities he may want to embark upon.

Nwafor (2013) views pension reform in Nigeria as parametric reform, this involves adjustments to the parameters of the pension systems such as increase in retirement age, reduction in annual accrual factor, change in benefit indexation and increase in contribution rate. This shows that several pension reform Acts may experience the same problem of its predecessor in Nigeria.

Types of Pension Reform Options

There are two broad types of pension reform. These are: parametric and the systematic pension reforms. Parametric reforms involve adjustments to the parameters of the

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pension system such as retirement age, contribution rate, etc. These adjustments which may be ad hoc or discretionary tend to create uncertainty and problem in the system. On the other hand, systematic reform involves a complete shift in the pension systems by a country for example, from defined benefit system to the defined contributory system or social pension or voluntary pension scheme. Systematic reform could be single-pillar or multi-pillars depending on the contribution of the various systems, e.g., Nigeria (2004), Chile (1980), Argentina (1994) but it reversed later in 2007.

Basically, Nigeria embarked on multi-pillars, systematic pension reform, changing completely from the defined benefit to the defined contributory scheme. It has an individual's Retirement Savings Accounts (RSA), valued arrangement taking various forms (individuals, employer sponsored, defined benefit and defined contributory) which are flexible and discretionary in nature and informed intra-family or inter-generational sources of both financial and non-financial support to the elderly, including adequate health care.

Other key options in the new pension scheme (contributory pension scheme) are:

- I. Nature of the scheme:** The new pension scheme is a Contributory Pension Scheme (Section 1 Part of PRA 2004), for the payment of retirement benefits of employees who are eligible under the scheme.
- ii. Rate of contribution:** Section 9 (1) specifies the contribution by the individual and the employer as follows:
 - a. In the case of public service of the Federation and the Federal Capital Territory, a minimum of 7.5% by the employer and a minimum of 7.5% by the employee.
 - b. In the case of the military, a minimum of 12.5% by the employer and a minimum of 2.5% by the employee.
 - c. In other cases, a minimum of 7.5% by the employer and a minimum of 7.5% by the employee.

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Objectives of pension reform

The objectives of the scheme according to section 2, part 1 of PRA of 2004 include to:

- i. ensure every person who has worked receives retirement benefit as and where due (to reduce old age poverty);
- ii. assist improvident individuals to save towards old age (saving grows economy & deepens financial markets);
- iii. establish a uniform set of rules, regulation and standards for administration and payments of pension.

Contributory Pensions Reforms and its Practice in Nigeria

Commitment of workers to entity's goals (which involves attitudes towards organization objectives) is one of the critical success factors of the organization. Nwafor (2014) opined that commitment that spurs employees to achieve set objectives of an organization is linked to motivation. Pension is one of the motivating factors. Pension and other retirement benefits have effects on the commitment of employees. He further added that a good pension scheme influences how a worker will perform his job. To Eme and Sam (2011), a good pension scheme should guarantee better life after active service and should help the employees to adjust properly into the society after retirement.

Olanrewaju (2011) opines that pension schemes should contribute to total well beings of the retirees. In his investigation, he established that Pension Reform Act, 2004 had contributed to social security of retirees at old age. Since retirement is a common destiny of employees, there should be a safe haven for employees after retirement (Omoni, 2013). The positive thing that the Federal government of Nigeria has done about pension reform matter is the introduction of the contributory pension scheme through the pension reform Act, 2004 which commenced in June of that same year. The CPS requires a civilian employee who is not a daily paid or casual worker, and the employer in either the public or private sector organization to contribute to the scheme. The employee and the employer are to contribute a minimum of seven and a half percent (7.5%) each of the employee's consolidated monthly emoluments or the employer alone can contribute the minimum fifteen per cent (15%) to the employee's pension fund. For the armed forces, the government contributes twelve and a half percent (12 1/2%) and

the armed forces personnel contribute two and a half percent (2 1/2%). Those exempted from the scheme are the Chief Justice of Nigeria, a Justice of the Supreme Court, President of the Court of Appeal, a Justice of the Court of Appeal, 'who retires at or after the age of sixty-five years'.

Under the Pension Reform Act, 2004, employees are now given privilege to select the Pension Fund Administrators of their choices. This gives opportunity to prospective pensioners to monitor their pension contributions even while in active service. Withdrawal can also be made from the pension contribution by the employee in as much as he or she has reached the age of fifty years before retirement. Edogbanya (2013) listed some of the prospects of the defined contributory scheme to include:

- i. Intensified public education and enlightenment.
- ii. Strong support from and collaboration with stakeholders.
- iii. Consistent support and strong political will from the executive and legislative arms of government.
- iv. Gradual adoption of the new scheme by other tier of government especially state government.

Contributing Pension Reform and Pensioners' Welfare in Nigeria: the Missing Link

Without a doubt, employees are entitled to various benefits. Among these benefits is pension. Pension is one of the motivating factors to enhance high productivity, loyalty and discipline of the employees (Umar and Tsado, 2012). In order to enforce this compulsory saving toward life after active service, government designed various policies and schemes to improve the standard of living of pensioners after active service. Experience and even literatures have shown that lives after active services have always proven unpleasant for pensioners even in spite of various schemes and frequent changes in pension systems. These could be traced to various setbacks encountered by pension schemes in Nigeria right from inception in 1951 till 2014. These problems range from inadequate fund, proliferation of ineligible pensioners on the payroll, poor management of pension fund, etc.

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In order to address this, pension reform Act, 2004 was introduced. To Anazodo, Ezenwile, Chidolue and Chidinma (2014), the advent of 2004 Pension Reform Act received massive support among employees and pensioners who witnessed limitations of the last reform Act. However, despite the wide acceptability of the contributor pension scheme by most pensioners, the scheme is overruled by various challenges and lapses ranging from weak administration, lack of records keeping, corruption, among others (Ohai and Awoyinfa, 2013). Pension Reform Act, (2004) followed suits of its predecessor scheme. There was loss of confidence in Pension Fund Administrators and Custodians, as many pensioners experienced delay in payment of pension and life became more unbearable for pensioners.

Omoni, (2013) traced the lapses of Pension Reform Act, 2004 to little or no awareness and uncertainty of the retirement years. He further opines that the transitional challenges in the new pension scheme (contributory pension) include the following:

- i. Knowledge gap and general misconceptions.
- ii. Widening the coverage in the informal and private sector, many of the SMEs, private, small business are not yet to buy the idea.
- iii. Securing system wide buy-in and initial reluctance from employees to register with PFAs.
- iv. Capacity building in the new pension industry.
- v. Quantifying and transferring legacy funds and asset managed by employees, insurance companies and pension managers.

Meng (2010) pointed to other areas which require further strengthening in order to make the new pension scheme effective and efficient to include:

- i. Durability pension for employees who sustain minor or permanent injury/disability in the course of their duties.
- ii. In respect of section 71 (1) of the PRA, relevant guideline stipulated in the number of years an RSA holder is expected to contribute to be qualified for the Minimum Guarantee Pension (MGP).
- iii. The full involvement of state and local government in the new contribution

pension scheme to include the large number of public sector employees currently not within PRA of 2004.

- iv. Enrichment and adequate funding of the data base by PENCOM.

Empirical Literature Review

Nwanne (2015) examined the impact of contributory pension scheme on economic growth in Nigeria for the period of 2004 and 2012 using ex-post facto research design. Panel data extracted from pension bulletins were analyzed using OLS regression. The study found that contributory pension scheme has achieved the objective of using pension funds to provide long term capital that will promote economic growth.

Mathew and Emmanuel (2019) carried out a study on Evaluation of the benefits of the old and the new pension schemes in Nigeria. The study examines the difference between the retirement benefit of the old 'pay-as-you-go' pension scheme, and the new 'contributory' pension scheme (CPS). The data used in the study were obtained indirectly from secondary sources. In the study, the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and the Pearson Correlation methods were employed, aided by the SPSS for the purpose of data analysis. The study found that the financial value of the retirement benefit of the old pension scheme is significantly higher than that of the new pension scheme. The study also found that the benefits of the two pension schemes significantly follow the same trend. The study concluded that the new pension scheme pays out a lesser amount of the retirement benefit than the old. The study provided recommendations for the efficient management of the investments in the pension fund so as to achieve a sufficient return in order to bridge the gap with respect to the retirement benefit between the two pension plans.

Folayan, Okewole and Bamidele (2020) carried out a study to examine the effect of pension reforms on pensioners' standards of livings in Local government councils within Oke Ogun axis, Oyo State, Nigeria. It was found that pension scheme reforms have significant and positive effect on pensioners' standards of living. The study maintained that in spite of various reforms introduced to the pension scheme, the stories of pensioners remained the same. To achieve the objective of the study, survey designed was adopted using the primary data gathered through administration of questionnaires

to one hundred and fifty pensioners selected from five local government councils within Oke Ogun using stratified sampling technique. Data were analyzed using multiple regression analysis. Productivity theory of Pension was adopted as a theory framework. The major finding of the study maintained that pensioners were not adequately educated on the effect of the pension scheme reforms on their standards of living. It was therefore, recommended that pensioners should be properly educated on various reforms relating to pension scheme.

Ebere (2016) carried out a survey on Pension Reforms in Nigeria. The study maintained that both public and private sectors have failed to live up to the financial and development aspirations of the pensioners in Nigeria. According to him, the compliance ratios of 7.5% of the contribution from both the employers and the employees have been low because of a lack of effective regulation and supervisory mechanism for the contributory pension system. To achieve the objective of the study, the researcher adopted historical and survey research method. Data were drawn from both primary and secondary sources. It was concluded from the findings of the study that factors such as the nature of retirement, size of family, level of income and level of education are significant indices that determine the level of adjustment among the retired Civil Servants. Based on the findings, the study recommended, among others, that various establishments in Nigeria should be encouraged to organize retirement counseling for their workers to enable them prepare for the obvious eventuality.

Theoretical Framework

This research is hinged on Productivity theory of Pension as propounded by Dorsey, Cornwell and Macpherson (1998). Productivity theory of pension is of two sides: the demand and supply sides. Both sides of the theory however, agreed that pension schemes are established as incentives and motivation to encourage workers to increase their productivity or performance (Nwafor, 2013). The demand side of the theory posits that employers make payments to employees' pension funds because workers are keen on or prefer pension savings to cash payments to their emoluments. This is because of the benefits attached. These include reduction in income tax of the employee, the retirement benefits, such as social security from the employer's contributions, interest earnings and dividend earnings on pension fund investment or assets that are not taxed.

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Others include the prospect of future enhanced and acceptable pension benefits, from awards or increases as may be offered by the government from time to time. Yet another benefit is an insurance cover of sorts against risks that pension provides.

Nwafor (2013) posits that the demand side also states that employees, especially the high income earners, prefer pension to cash payments because of a possible annuity for as long as the pensioner lives. There is the shifting of risk of poor asset or investment performance to the employer in Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS), which is not exactly so in the CPS where there is a PFA. In the CPS, it is the asset earnings that are distributed to contributors or pensioners. Thus, risk shifting is easier to operate in a DBPS where there is a promised or defined benefit than in CPS where the value of the benefit is a function of the value of the asset or pension fund performance.

Finally, on the demand side, there is the potential of improved performance or output of the employee merely by the institution of a pension fund or scheme. The implication of this is that the pension scheme must be well articulated; involve the workers in the decision processes; well-funded and sustainable such that it can motivate the workers or employees.

The supply side of this theory posits that employees' gain from pension tends to raise the level of workforce productivity and reduce labour costs. This is because the employers' investments in the training of the workforce improved condition of service, provision of adequate resources, etc., are greatly offset by the workforce's improved output or productivity. There is also the perspective that the supply side to the theory serves as an incentive for personnel to remain in the organization for a long time. This means that there is a reduced personnel turnover as DBPS penalizes organization quits. In all this, the organization tends to gain, however, because of large workforce's high productivity and attachment to the organization (Nwafor, 2013).

Testing of Research Hypotheses

Testing of Hypothesis 1: Non-remittance of counterpart contribution by Employers tends to affect pensioners' Welfare in Nigeria.

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Distribution of the Observed and Expected Frequencies for hypothesis 1

S/N	Statement	SA	A	SD	D	Total
9	Insincerity on the side of the employers (government) to contribute their monthly emolument as part of their CPS requirement as stated by 2004 pension Act, negatively affect workers' livelihood after retirement in Nigeria.	124 (31)	110 (27.5)	23 (5.75)	17 (4.25)	274
10	Lateness in released of counterpart funding by Nigerian government into contributory pension account of each retiree worsens the level of which pensioners are paid as well as taken care of in Nigeria.	120 (30)	124 (31)	19 (4.75)	11 (2.75)	274
11	Lack of adequate data and information needed affect the level to which government plans for her retirees in Nigeria	110 (27.5)	124 (31)	17 (4.25)	23 (5.75)	274
12	Delay in pension payment and unsatisfying nature of pension schemes is as a result of non-compliance by most employers in Nigeria	113 (28.25)	131 (32.75)	17 (4.25)	13 (3.25)	274

Table 4.2.2: Chi-square calculation for hypothesis 1

	SA	A	SD	D	Total	X ² Cal.	X ² Tab.
9	124	110	23	17	274		
10	120	124	19	11	274		
11	110	124	17	23	274		
12	113	131	17	13	274		
Total	467	489	76	64	1096	2141.07	16.919

$$\chi^2 = 2141.07$$

$$d/f = (R-1)(C-1)$$

$$= (4-1)(4-1)$$

$$= 3 \times 3 = 9$$

$$TV = 16.919$$

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Chi-square Calculation

R – C	Fo	Fe	Fo – Fe	(Fo – Fe) ²	$\frac{(Fo - Fe)^2}{Fe}$
9-1	124	31	93	8649	279
9-2	110	27.5	82.5	6806.25	247.5
9-3	23	5.75	17.25	297.56	51.75
9-4	17	4.25	12.75	162.56	38.25
10-1	120	30	90	8100	270
10-2	124	31	93	8649	279
10-3	19	4.75	14.25	203.06	42.75
10-4	11	2.75	8.25	68.06	24.75
11-1	110	27.5	82.5	6806.25	247.5
11-2	124	31	93	8649	279
11-3	17	4.25	12.75	162.56	38.25
11-4	23	5.75	17.25	297.56	51.75
12-1	113	28.25	80.25	6440.06	227.97
12-2	131	32.75	98.25	9653.06	294.75
12-3	17	4.25	12.75	162.56	38.25
12-4	13	3.25	9.75	95.06	25.35
Total					2141.07

Source: *Field Work 2022*

Decision

Table 4.5 above shows that the computed (χ^2) value of 2141.07 is greater than the critical value of 16.919 in the statistical table at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that alternative hypothesis (Hi) is accepted against the null hypothesis (Ho), meaning that non-remittance of counterpart contribution by employers negatively affect pensioners' welfare in Nigeria.

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Evaluation of Hypothesis II: Corrupt practices among pension administrators tend to affect pensioners' welfare Nigeria Distribution of the Observed and Expected Frequencies for hypothesis II.

S/N	Statement	SA	A	SD	D	Total
1	Corruption among pension officers significantly affect the efficiency level of contributory pension scheme in Nigeria.	121 (30.25)	118 (29.5)	20 (5)	15 (3.75)	274
2	An act of diverting funds set aside by the government as pension by those entrusted to manage such funds negatively affect pensioners source of livelihood in Nigeria.	119 (29.75)	124 (31)	17 (4.25)	14 (3.5)	274
3.	Inability of the government and its agencies to monitor and regulate the activities of pension administrators encouraged corruption and miss - appropriation of funds meant for pensioners in Nigeria.	142 (35.5)	118 (29.5)	8 (2)	6 (1.5)	274
4	Appointment of a person or group of persons into pension board as a means of settlement by the government negatively encouraged corruption and reduce the reliability of pension administration in Nigeria.	110 (27.5)	132 (33)	17 (4.25)	15 (3.75)	274

Table 4.2.2: Chi-square calculation for hypothesis II

	SA	A	SD	D	Total	X ² Cal.	X ² Tab.
1	121	118	20	15	274		
2	119	124	17	14	274		
3	142	118	8	6	274		
4	110	132	17	15	274		
Total	492	492	62	50	1096	2486.4	16.919

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$$\chi^2 = 2486.4$$

$$d/f = (R-1)(C-1)$$

$$= (4-1)(4-1)$$

$$= 3 \times 3 = 9$$

$$TV = 16.919$$

Chi-square Calculation

R - C	Fo	Fe	Fo - Fe	(Fo - Fe) ²	(Fo - Fe) ² / Fe
1-1	121	30.25	90.75	8235.56	272.25
1-2	118	29.5	88.5	7832.25	265.5
1-3	20	5	15	225	45
1-4	18	3.75	14.25	203.06	54.15
2-1	119	29.75	89.25	7965.56	267.75
2-2	124	31	93	8649	279
2-3	17	4.25	12.75	162.56	38.25
2-4	14	3.5	10.5	110.25	31.5
3-1	142	35.5	106.5	11342.25	319.5
3-2	118	29.5	88.5	7832.25	265.5
3-3	8	2	6	36	18
3-4	6	1.5	4.5	20.25	13.5
4-1	110	27.5	82.5	6806.25	247.5
4-2	132	33	99	9801	297
4-3	17	4.25	12.75	162.56	38.25
4-4	15	3.75	11.25	126.56	33.75
Total					2486.4

Source: Field Work 2022

Decision

Table 4.5 above shows that the computed (χ^2) value of 2486.4 is greater than the critical value of 16.919 in the statistical table at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that alternative hypothesis (H_1) is accepted against null hypothesis (H_0) which implies that corrupt practices among pension administrators and managers negatively affect pensioners' welfare in Nigeria

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Testing of Hypothesis III: Weak Pension Administration is likely to Affect the Level of Contributory Pension Scheme efficiency in Nigeria.

Distribution of the Observed and Expected Frequencies for hypothesis III

S/N	Statement	SA	A	SD	D	Total
5	Weak administration of contributory pension scheme by the pension administrators and government negatively affect the scheme efficiency in Nigeria	124 (31)	110 (27.5)	23 (5.75)	17 (4.25)	274
6	Inability to adhere to stringent laws and regulations governed the operation of CPS by the employers and employees affect the scheme smooth operation and functionality in Nigeria	120 (30)	124 (31)	19 (4.75)	11 (2.75)	274
7	Insincerity on the side of the employers (government) to contribute their monthly emolument as part their CPS requirement as stated by 2004 pension Act, negatively affect workers' livelihood after retirement in Nigeria.	110 (27.5)	124 (31)	17 (4.25)	23 (5.75)	274
8	Delay in pension payment and unsatisfying nature of pension schemes is as a result of poor and weak pension administration caused by incompetency on the side of government agencies mandated to over see pension activities as well as pensioners' welfare in Nigeria	113 (28.25)	131 (32.75)	17 (4.25)	13 (3.25)	274

Table 4.2.2: Chi-square calculation for hypothesis III

	SA	A	SD	D	Total	X ² Cal.	X ² Tab.
5	124	110	23	17	274		
6	120	124	19	11	274		
7	110	124	17	23	274		
8	113	131	17	13	274		
Total	467	489	76	64	1096	2141.07	16.919

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$$\chi^2 = 2141.07$$

$$d/f = (R-1)(C-1)$$

$$= (4-1)(4-1)$$

$$= 3 \times 3 = 9$$

$$TV = 16.919$$

Chi-square Calculation

R – C	Fo	Fe	Fo – Fe	(Fo – Fe) ²	$\frac{(Fo - Fe)^2}{Fe}$
5-1	124	31	93	8649	279
5-2	110	27.5	82.5	6806.25	247.5
5-3	23	5.75	17.25	297.56	51.75
5-4	17	4.25	12.75	162.56	38.25
6-1	120	30	90	8100	270
6-2	124	31	93	8649	279
6-3	19	4.75	14.25	203.06	42.75
6-4	11	2.75	8.25	68.06	24.75
7-1	110	27.5	82.5	6806.25	247.5
7-2	124	31	93	8649	279
7-3	17	4.25	12.75	162.56	38.25
7-4	23	5.75	17.25	297.56	51.75
8-1	113	28.25	80.25	6440.06	227.97
8-2	131	32.75	98.25	9653.06	294.75
8-3	17	4.25	12.75	162.56	38.25
8-4	13	3.25	9.75	95.06	25.35
Total					2141.07

Source: *Field Work 2022*

Decision

Table 4.5 above shows that the computed (χ^2) value of 2141.07 is greater than the critical value of 16.919 in the statistical table at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that alternative hypothesis (H_1) is accepted against the null hypothesis (H_0) which means that weak pension administration drastically affects the level to which contributory pension scheme function effectively and efficiently in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

This research explored the current literature on pension reform scheme and pensioners' welfare in Nigeria. Findings from the literature reviewed corroborated with the research findings which revealed that poor funding, weak management of pension funds, as well as corrupt practices among pension administrators significantly affect the extent to which contributory pension scheme can address the problems of pensioners in Nigeria. Sadly, the study discovered that life after active services are unpleasant for pensioners even in spite of various schemes and frequent changes in pension reforms. Also, despite the introduction of 2004 pension Reform Act (contributory pension scheme) which received massive support among employees and pensioners, followed suits of its predecessor scheme. The scheme which is characterized with delay in payment, weak administration, lack of records keeping, corruption, among others, cause many retirees to lose confidence due to its inability to address the problem of retirees in Nigeria.

The three hypotheses formulated for the study were evaluated and the results showed that contributory pension scheme is confronted with several challenges ranging from corruption to weak administration as well as poor funding, among others, as could be evidenced from χ^2 value. While evaluating hypothesis one which states that corrupt practices among pension administrators tend to affect pensioners' welfare in Nigeria, it was observed to negatively affect the extent to which contributory pension reform live to expectations. The study discovered that the problem of pension in Nigeria is significantly linked to insincerity of those entrusted to oversee the welfare of pensioners in the country as most of them are in the habit of diverting funds meant for pension to their personal self-aggrandizement, leaving the pensioners who served the country diligently in abject poverty.

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In analyzing hypotheses two, it was discovered that weak pension administration is likely to affect the level of contributory pension scheme efficiency in Nigeria. The null hypothesis was rejected, while the alternative hypothesis was upheld. Hypothesis three which stated that poor management of contributory pension funds tends to affect the level of pensioners' welfare in Nigeria, revealed in affirmation that it significantly affects the level of the pension scheme effectiveness and operation in Nigeria. Thus, leading to poor welfare and sustainability of most pensioners in Nigeria and Akwa Ibom State in particular.

This result is in line with Ohai and Awoyinfa (2013) who opined that the problems associated with effective administration of contributory pension scheme in Nigeria is as a result of weak administration, lack of record keeping, corruption, among others. Omoni, (2013) in his suggestions, traced the lapses of contributory pension Reform Act, 2004 to poor funding as well as little or no awareness and uncertainty of the scheme. He further added that many private sectors and small and medium business operators are not yet to buy the idea. Similarly, Eme and Sam (2011) traced the challenges of the scheme to the problem of quantifying and transferring legacy funds and assets managed by employees, insurance companies and pension in Nigeria

Conclusion

The study examined the effect of Pension Reform Act on Pensioners' Standard of Living with reference to Contributory Pension Scheme in Nigeria. The study focused on the major difference between the old Pension Reform and Pension Reform Act of 2004. The finding of the study established that contributory Pension Reform Act has no significant effect on the standards of living of pensioners in Nigeria. To substantiate this fact, the study evaluated the challenges faced by the contributory pension scheme and the difference between the retirement benefit of the old pension scheme plan and the new in Nigeria. Based on the evaluation, the study concludes that the contributory pension scheme in Nigeria has not addressed the pensioners' challenges as experienced in the old pension scheme. Sadly, instead of bringing new hope to retirees' welfare, the newly adopted pension system followed suits of its predecessor scheme. Many retirees have lost confidence on the pension model due to its inability to address the problem of

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retirees in Nigeria. In addition, the contributory pension scheme is characterized by non-remittance of the 7.7% counterpart contribution by most employers, delay in payment, weak administration, lack of records keeping, inadequate funding, inadequate subvention and grant, poor documentation, constant political manipulation, inaccurate record keeping that gives opportunities for corruption, among others of which was the major feature of the old pension models. These in turn bring hardship, suffering and untimely death among vast number of Nigerian pensioners.

Recommendations

Based on the above findings, the study recommends the following:

- i. The government should minimize the 'bottleneck' that is usually involved in payment of gratuity. Gratuity should be paid within a month after leaving the service. Hence, government should try and pay their counterpart contribution to workers' pension account for effective management of pensioners when retired.
- ii. The administration and management of Pension Fund should be given to Private Pension Administrators with credible records in order to forestall mismanagement of Pension Fund in Nigeria.
- iii. Efficient management of investments in the pension fund should be put in place so as to be able to achieve sufficient return in order to bridge the gap in the retirement benefit between the pension plans.
- iv. The various establishments in Nigeria should be encouraged to organize retirement

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